

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some Novel Amino Acid and Phosphazane Derivatives of 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin

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Manuscript received 10 June 1997, accepted 28 August 1997

Some new amino acids, tosyl- or phthalylamino acids and phosph(v)azane derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2-21) have been prepared and their biological activities evaluated.

Coumarin derivatives are known to have antifungal and antibacterial properties¹. Combination of amino acids with substituted coumarins affords compounds of interesting biological properties². On the other hand, the phosph(v)azanes derivatives have been used as agricultural insecticides³. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to prepare better therapeutically active compounds.

Some new amino acids and phosph(v)azanes derivatives of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1) have been synthesised. Interaction of 1 with free amino acid in presence of formalin afforded the corresponding Mannich bases (2-5).

2 A = Gly 3 A = L-Ala
4 A = L-Phe 5 A = PABA

The tosyl- or phthalylaminoacylcoumarin derivatives (6-13) were obtained via the condensation of 1 with the requisite tosyl- or phthalylamino acid using the acid chloride procedure.

6 A = Tos.Gly 7 A = Tos.L-Ala
8 A = Tos.L-Phe 9 A = Tos.PABA
10 A = Pht.Gly 11 A = Pht.L-Ala.
12 A = Pht.L-Phe 13 A = Pht.PABA

Treatment of 1 with 1,3-diaryl-2,2,2,4,4,4-hexachloro- or 2,4-dithio-2,4-dichlorocyclodiphosph(v)azanes produced 1,3-diaryl-2,4-(4-methyl-7-coumarinoxy)-2,2,4,4-tetrachloro- or 2,4-dithiocyclodiphosph(v)azanes (14-21).

Biological screening : The antimicrobial activities of the compounds were determined using the hole plate and the filter paper disc methods⁷. All the synthesised compounds were tested against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Es-*

14 R = H, X = 2Cl 15 R = o-Cl, X = 2Cl
16 R = p-Cl, X = 2Cl 17 R = p-CH₃, X = 2Cl
18 R = H, X = S 19 R = o-Cl, X = S
20 R = p-Cl, X = S 21 R = p-CH₃, X = S

cherichia coli, *Serratia marcesens* and fungi *Candida utilis*. A qualitative screen was performed on all compounds while quantitative assays were done on active compounds only (Table 1).

TABLE I—BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA (MIC, mg ml⁻¹) OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	B.s	B.m	E.c	S.n	C.u
2	100	150	—	200	—
4	50	100	150	—	—
6	—	—	—	125	—
10	125	125	—	—	—
11	125	125	—	—	—
14	125	50	125	50	200
15	50	50	100	100	150
16	50	50	150	125	150
17	150	100	150	100	200
18	150	125	150	100	—
19	100	50	100	150	200
20	50	50	100	200	200
21	200	100	150	150	—

Experimental

M.ps. were taken on an electric SMP1 apparatus and are uncorrected. Microanalyses were performed in Microanalytical Research Center, Cairo University. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-FTIR-2000 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a FX 90 Q Fourier spectrometer, mass spectra on Shimadzu GC-MS-QP 100 Ex spectrometer and electronic spectra on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-3B spectrophotometer using DMF as a solvent.

7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1)⁴ and 1,3-diaryl-2,2,

2,4,4,4-hexachloro- or 2,4-dithio-2,4-dichlorocyclodiphosph(v)azanes⁵ were prepared by the reported methods.

N-(7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-coumarinyl)amino acid derivatives (2-5). *General procedure*: A mixture of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (**1**; 0.01 mol), amino acid (0.01 mol) and formalin (40%, 1.2 ml) in 80% ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4-6 h. The product separated during reflux was then filtered, extracted with ethanol to remove unreacted coumarin and crystallised: **2** (79%), m.p. 252-54° (DMF), ν_{\max} 3420 (OH), 3362 (NH), 3041, 1600 (CH and C=C of aromatic nucleus), 2958, 2897 (CH, aliphatic), 1721 (lactonic C=O of coumarin ring) and 1594 cm^{-1} (carboxylate anion), m/z M^+ , 263 (4.3), 219 (20.2) 205 (8.0), 189 (55.4), 160 (100), 132 (18.9), 103 (34.2) and 77 (43.6%); **3** (81%), 246-48° (DMF), δ (DMSO- s_6 /TMS) 1.8 (3H, d, CHCH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.6 (1H, q, CHCH₃), 5.1 (2H, br, CH₂NH), 6.4 (1H, s, C₃-H), 7.4 (2H, m, ArH); **4** (71%), 195-97° (DMF); **5** (64%), 244-46° (DMF).

7-*o*-(Tosyl- or phthalylaminoacyl)-4-methylcoumarin derivatives (6-13). *General procedure*: A solution of freshly prepared *N*-tosyl- or phthalylaminoacyl chloride⁶ (0.05 mol) in dry dioxane was added dropwise to a stirred cold solution of **1** (0.05 mol) in dry dioxane containing Et₃N (0.055 mol). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3-4 h and then left overnight at room temperature. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residual solid was purified by recrystallization from the proper solvent: **6** (54%), m.p. 113-15° (EtOH-H₂O), ν_{\max} 3061 (CH, aromatic), 3281 (NH of sulphonamide), 1730 (C=O) and 1322, 1119 cm^{-1} (S=O); **7** (49%), 198-200° (EtOH-H₂O); **8** (64%), 216-18° (EtOH-H₂O); **9** (74%), 259-61° (EtOH); **10** (73%), 194-96° (EtOH-H₂O), δ (DMSO- d_6) 2.5 (3H, s, C₄-CH₃), 4.6 (2H, s, NCH₂CO), 6.3 (1H, s, C₃-H) and 7.3-8.1 (7H, m, ArH); **11** (82%), 143-45° (EtOH-H₂O); **12** (68%), 151-53° (EtOH-H₂O); **13** (91%), 179-81° (EtOH).

1,3-Diaryl-2,4-di(4-methyl-7-coumarinoxy)-2,2,4,4-tetra-chloro- or 2,4-dithiocyclodiphosph(v)azanes derivatives (14-21). *General procedure*: 7-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (**1**; 0.01 mol) was added in small portions to a

well-stirred solution of 1,3-diaryl-2,2,2,4,4,4-hexachloro- or 2,4-dithio-2,4-dichlorodiphosph(v)azane (0.01 mol) in dry benzene. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 6 h under anhydrous conditions. After completion of the reaction (HCl gas ceased to evolve), the mixture was filtered hot. The solid obtained after cooling was washed several times with dry benzene and diethyl ether and dried under reduced pressure: **14** (60%), m.p. 196-98°, ν_{\max} 3054, 1611 (CH, C=C of aromatic nucleus), 2965 (CH₃), 1714 (C=O, coumarin), 1054 (P-O-C), 1092 (P-N) and 515 cm^{-1} (P-Cl); **15** (54%), 136-38°; **16** (32%), 154-56°; **17** (41%), 185-87°, δ (DMSO- d_6) 0.92 (6H, s, 2CH₃ of dimer), 2.3 (6H, s, 2C₄-CH₃), 6.3 (2H, s, 2C₃-H), 7.3-8.6 (12H, m, ArH), m/z 574 (34.1), 572 (100), 398 (4.9), 307 (11.1), 278 (10.3), 176 (41.6), 147 (80.5) and 103 (30.2%); **18** (44%), 115-17°, ν_{\max} 3069 (CH aromatic), 1717 (C=O coumarin), 1058 (P-O-C), 1095 (P-N), 773 cm^{-1} (P=S); **19** (30%), 121-23°; **20** (41%), 149-51°; **21** (51%), 225-27°. The uv-spectra of compounds **14-21** showed the characteristic bands of the phosph(v)azane four-membered ring at 260-290 nm.

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